

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2022-3>

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ISSN: 2181-9297

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Gaybullayeva Malokhat Pulatovna

Teacher of the Department of Roman-german philology

Karshi State University

malohatgaybullayeva@gmail.com

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH DIALECTS
 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642594>
ABSTRACT

A similar concern for durability and respectability underlay the new preoccupation with orthography. Early spelling reformers, especially printers, sought to replace the largely idiosyncratic practices that had sufficed in the preprinting era with a common system that seemed to them to be related to the sound system in a more consistent way. A complex process that led to an altered distribution of all the long vowels of English, known to philologists as the Great Vowel Shift, began in the latter part of the Middle English period.

For instance, language is a social phenomenon that has been created and refined by the whole society, not by a particular group, in the course of the historical development of human society. At the same time, language is not the product of one period, of any socio-economic society, but the history of society as a whole.

Key words: sound system, distribution, historical dimension, variation, endeavor

G'aybullayeva Malohat Pulatovna

Roman-german filologiyasi kafedrasi o'qituvchisi

Qarshi davlat universiteti

malohatgaybullayeva@gmail.com

INGLIZ DIALEKTLARINING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISHI**ANNOTASIYA**

Orfografiya bilan bog'liq yangi mashg'ulotlarning asosida davomiylik va asos kabi masala yotadi. Ilk imlo islohotchilari, ayniqsa matbuotchilar avvalgi davrlarda yetarlicha bo'lganligiga qaramay, ular asosan bosmaxonada o'ziga xos usullarni ya'ni, tovush tizimi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan muammolarni o'zgartirishga intilishgan. Filologlar ingliz tilidagi barcha cho'ziq tovush unllilarining o'zgarishini tahlil qilishni asosan O'rta ingliz davrining so'nggi qismida boshlashgan.

Chunonchi, til kishilik jamiyatining tarixiy taraqqiyoti jarayonida ma'lum bir guruh tomonidan emas, balki butun jamiyat tomonidan yaratilgan, sayqal topgan ijtimoiy hodisadir. Shu bilan birga, til biror davrning, biror ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jamiyatning mahsuli bo'lmay, balki butun jamiyat tarixi jarayonidagi bir qancha davrlarning mahsulidir.

Kalit so'zlar: tovush tizimi, tarqalish, tarixiy o'lchov, o'zgaruvchanlik, harakat

Гайбуллаева Малохат Пулатовна
преподаватель кафедры Романо-германской филологии
Каршинский государственный университет
malohatgaybullayeva@gmail.com

ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ АНГЛИЙСКИХ ДИАЛЕКТОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Подобная забота о долговечности и респектабельности лежала в основе нового увлечения орфографией. Ранние реформаторы орфографии, особенно печатники, стремились заменить в значительной степени идиосинкразические методы, которых было достаточно в эпоху допечатной подготовки, общей системой, которая, как им казалось, более последовательно связана со звуковой системой. Известные филологи начали работать сложный процесс, как приведший к изменению распределения всех долгих гласных в английском языке во второй половине среднеанглийского периода.

Например, язык — это социальное явление, созданное и усовершенствованное всем обществом, а не отдельной группой, в ходе исторического развития человеческого общества. В то же время язык является продуктом не одного периода, какого-либо социально-экономического общества, а нескольких периодов истории общества в целом.

Ключевые слова: звуковая система, распространение, историческое измерение, вариация, стремление.

It was not possible to deduce the existence of this family of languages until the scholars became aware of systematic resemblances which can be found between European languages and Sanskrit, the ancient attested language of the Indian sub-continent. When this were first noticed in the 16th century, many people thought that Sanskrit was the parent of the European languages. But towards at the end of the 18th century the systematic studies began which showed conclusively that this was not the case. Following an early statement of common origin hypothesis in 1786, by Sir William Jones (1746-94), the British orientalist and jurist, the early 19th century producer several major works which laid the foundation Indo-European philology. In his presidential address to the Bengal Asiatic Society in 1786 he mentioned his following observation and generally quoted as the first clear statement asserting the existence of Indo-European: ‘The Sanskrit language, whatever be its antiquity, is of a wonderful structure; more perfect than the Greek, more copious (rich) than the Latin, and more exquisitely refined than either yet bearing to both of them stronger affinity, both in the roots of verbs, and in the forms of grammar than could possibly have been produced by accident; so strong indeed that no philologist could examine them all three without believing to have sprung from the some common source which perhaps, no longer exists’. In 1816 the German philologist Franz Bopp published a study whose scope is well illustrated by its title: ‘On the conjugation system of Sanskrit language, in comparison with those of the Greek, Latin, Persian, and Germanic languages’.

The relationships of the Germanic languages of Latin, Greek, Slavic and Baltic languages was demonstrated in a work written in 1814 by the Danish linguist Rasmus Rask but not published until 1818, ‘Investigation on the origin of the Old Norse or Icelandic language’. Further philological treatises followed, mainly written by Germans, such as Jacob Grimm and August Schleicher. In 1883, Franz Bopp began the publication of the first major Indo-European grammar: ‘Comparative Grammar of Sanskrit, Zend, Greek, Latin, Lithuanian, Old Slavic, Gothic and German’. It took 19 years to complete and by its 3rd edition incorporated Old Slavic, Celtic and Albanian. In due course this work and its contemporaries became out of date, as result of vast amount of philological study undertaken in the second half of the 19th century. A further publishing landmark was Karl Brugman’s ‘Outline of Comparative Indo-European Grammar’ (1867-1916). A ‘new Indo-European Grammar’, the outcome of a project directed by the Polish linguist, Jerzy Kurilowicz, commenced publication in 1968.

Jacob Grimm (1785-1863) Well-known to children everywhere for the collection of fairy tales and songs which he compiled with his brother. To linguists and philologists, he is also remembered for his major works in Germanic philology, especially his explanation of how the consonants of different Indo-European languages relate to each other. There is for example, a regular relationship between words beginning with 'p' in Latin and 'f' in Germanic languages as in (Lat. Pater-Eng. Father; Gr. Treis-Engl. Three). The rule governing these sound shifts became known as Grimm's law.

The arrival of the Vikings, who, until King Alfred's victory in 878, threatened to subjugate the newly Christianized English, resulted in further augmentation of the vocabulary. But the language they spoke, which had a strong influence upon English speech, particularly in the Danelaw, the area lying to the northeast of a line drawn from Chester to London, was closely related to it. The results of its admixture were subtler and elusive. Pairs of words, differentiated by a single sound, like skirt and shirt, whole and hale, have survived. Instead of a quasi- technical vocabulary associated with a new field of interest or endeavor, we have Old North borrowings that are every bit as commonplace as native Old English words: husband, ugly, call, want, and, most surprisingly, the pronouns they, them, and there to go alongside Old English he, him, and her. The effects of this kind of merging are not evident until we come to examine texts of the early Middle English period, and its thoroughness is such that we cannot always be sure to which of the two Germanic languages a particular word should be traced.

When William, Duke of Normandy, defeated the English king at Hastings in 1066, he inaugurated a period of rule by French-speaking kings and of pervasive domination by a nobility and clergy whose interests were predominantly in things French. Until King John lost the last of the continental possessions in 1205, Norman French was the language of the Court, of business, and of lay culture, while Latin remained the ecclesiastical language. English seems virtually to have been reduced to the role of a patois. Further contact with France, through royal marriages and through participation in the wider European cultural scene, of which French was the unchallenged medium, ensured that language retained its privileged position in the upper reaches of society right up to Chaucer's time, but alongside this the thirteenth century saw a gradual reinstatement of English. By this time, the language had undergone radical changes, some of which can be directly related to the long break in the literary tradition. The elaborate inflection system that had been so conspicuous a feature of Old English, manifested, for instance, in the six different forms of the noun stan (stone), may well have been undergoing simplification in the spoken language before the Norman Conquest. Absence of the conservative influences of the written form would undoubtedly accelerate the process: although some vestiges of inflectional endings survive until after Chaucer's time. Middle English is essentially without this refinement. Instead, the relations between content words are specified by a freer use of prepositions. Another change was largely due to the fact that the French-trained scribes, who now replaced those trained in the Old English tradition, introduced new orthographic conventions and in so doing were responsible for much of the inconsistency for which modern English spelling is notorious. New characters - k, g, q, v, w, z - were brought into use. As a consequence, the two pronunciations of Old English 'c' could now be differentiated, as in the modern spelling of king (from cyning) and choose (from ceosan). But the retention of 'c' in words like cat and its use to represent /s/ in nice have left the confusing results: can, cent. The characteristic Old English letters LP and ð were gradually replaced by th, and the loss of ȝ resulted in the sound it represented (a sound which was itself subsequently lost) being spelt as gh In words like night, daughter, and laugh. Finally, because of the similarity of a number of characters such as u, v, n, m, and w in the Carolingian script used by the scribes, u was replaced by o in many words like come, son, and wonder.

But by far the most noticeable feature of English, as it re-emerges after the period of the supremacy of French, was the very large number of French words that had been absorbed into the common stock. Many of these can be sorted into sets that correspond with activities in which the indigenous English speakers are thought to have played only minor parts. For instance, they include much of the modern vocabulary of government and law, of ecclesiastical and military matters, of art, learning, and medicine. Other words reflect an upper-class preoccupation with fashion, polite social

life, and refined feeding habits. A measure of the degree of assimilation of the new French words is the speed of their occurrence in derivatives, often taking English endings as in *gently* and *gentleness*, and forming hybrid compounds like *gentleman*. The early borrowings were naturally from Norman French, but later the source was predominantly the culturally more prestigious dialect of Central France. The borrowing, at different times, of related words from both dialects provided such differentiated forms as *cattle* and *chattel*, *warden* and *guard*. Generally, the massive accession of loan words seems to have inhibited the language's facility for creating new, self-explanatory compounds, a practice that was not revived extensively until the nineteenth century, when scientific and technological advances generated new needs.

A characteristic of Middle English was its very considerable regional variation. Contemporary writers testify that the speech of one area was frequently unintelligible to inhabitants of another. Amid the confusion, it is possible to distinguish five major areas: The North, extending as far as the number; the East and West Midlands, together extending from the number to the Thames; the South; and Kent. Each of these is represented in some part of the literary output that has survived, a situation that contrasts with the near monopoly of West Saxon as a literary dialect in the earlier. Old English, period. The end of the fourteenth century, however, saw the rise of Standard English, a result largely of the commercial supremacy of the East Midlands. In particular the growing importance of London as a political, judicial, social, and intellectual center led to the elevation of one particular variety of the East Midland dialect, namely London English, to a position of prestige that it has enjoyed ever since. It was this dialect that was to be used overwhelmingly when the invention of printing opened up unprecedented opportunities for disseminating the written word.

The printing press was one of the factors that, around 1500, resulted in the second great change in English. The need and the possibility of what we can properly think of as mass circulation placed a high premium on the use of the vernacular. As in other parts of Europe, the latter made incursions into territories in which Latin had formerly held sway: law, medicine, and religion in particular. And one aspect of the revival of interest in classical antiquity was the very considerable translating activity that gave Shakespeare, for instance, with his 'little Latin and less Greek', access too much of the classical heritage. Engagement with Latin and Greek had effects upon English, upon both vocabulary and grammar. The effects on vocabulary were more immediately noticeable and led to a further accession of new words, often those of a learned and polysyllabic kind, which, when carried to excess, earned contemporary castigation as 'inkhorn' terms. In this way, the classical experience may be said to have been a potent instrument of change. Its effect upon grammar, though less immediate, was, by contrast, conservative.

The increasing use of English in more scholarly contexts after 1500 resulted in misgivings about its ability to survive. Compared with the fixity and predictability of Ciceronian Latin - by now a well and truly 'dead' language - it seemed all too subject to change. The desire to 'fix' English, so that matter expressed in it would have the same chances of survival as that expressed in the ancient languages, led to attempts by grammarians to legislate for the user; the basis of their legislation was, understandably, the well-known syntax of Latin. A similar concern for durability and respectability underlay the new preoccupation with orthography. Early spelling reformers, especially printers, sought to replace the largely idiosyncratic practices that had sufficed in the preprinting era with a common system that seemed to them to be related to the sound system in a more consistent way. They were not helped in this enterprise - an enterprise that, incidentally, has continued to exercise the minds of language teachers ever since - by the fact that some of the sounds were themselves currently undergoing major changes. A complex process that led to an altered distribution of all the long vowels of English, known to philologists as the Great Vowel Shift, began in the latter part of the Middle English period but was not completed until after Shakespeare's time. For his audiences Rome rhymed with room, and raisin with reason. In bringing this sketch of the development of English up to the beginning of the Modern English period, we have already reached the stage where its internal history and its external history react upon each other. The astonishing - and as some thought - excessive openness of English to new vocabulary resulted in the adoption of words not only from every major European language, but also from the exotic languages of remoter lands to which

it was now being carried. In the following paragraphs we note something of the effects of local languages and local conditions upon the speech of English-speaking settlers across the world; they were felt not only in vocabulary, but in grammar and pronunciation also. An important aspect of the more recent development of British English has been its absorption of features from the new regional varieties to which geographical dispersion gave rise. Since no account of language development, however brief, can legitimately omit reference to attitudes, we must recognize that this last tendency has by no means always been welcomed by purists. And if a desire to protect the home-grown product from the effects of outside interference is questionable, the wish to prescribe standards for the much greater number of people who speak English outside the British Isles is even more so.

In the various forms that Standard English now takes, there are, in fact, only very slight differences in grammar, and the variations in pronunciation - the numerous local accents - represent no insuperable barrier to intelligibility, however forcibly they may impress themselves upon the listener. As for vocabulary, there is a central core of ordinary, most frequently used words that all geographically distinguished varieties of the standard language share. There is also a shared and continually growing lexicon of highly specialized and technical terms. Between these two lies a considerable body of moderately common words and idioms, and it is here that the major national and local distinctions are to be found: Americanisms, Australianisms, Scotticisms, and so on, all having their own peculiarities of usage.

The differences and distinctions we find in the use of English round the world seem hardly likely to wither away. Present conditions seem rather to indicate a gradual increase. Common sense seems to suggest willing acceptance of them as natural and interesting aspects of the language and of the individualities of the people who use it.

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МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

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